

THE ROLES OF TEACHERS AND STUDENTS IN CLASSROOM

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Abstract: Teaching can be either teacher-centered or student-centered or a combination of both. Teacher -centered teaching has been in practice for centuries. Learner-centered instruction, on the other hand is quite a recent approach growing. Now it seems to have won ground over traditional teacher-centered instruction in many educational institutions and among educationists ‘ circles in many parts of the world.

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Introduction. Learner-centeredness is the vogue of the day in the field of education in general and in second and foreign language instruction in particular. Teaching can be either teacher-centered or student-centered or a combination of both. Teacher-centered teaching has been in practice for centuries. Learner-centered instruction, on the other hand is quite a recent approach. It has been growing rapidly for the past three decades. Now it seems to have won ground over traditional teacher-centered instruction in many educational institutions and among educationists ‘ circles in many parts of the world. The shift of emphasis from teacher-centeredness to that of the centeredness of the learner is due to what is believed to be the failure of teacher-centered instruction style to prepare the learner to cope with the demands of the ever-changing and challenging life socially, politically and economically. At the same time, educators concerned with the growing problems of school dropout, low levels of academic achievement, and other indicators of school failure have been arguing for more learner-centered models of instruction. Such models attend to the diversity among students and

to the use this diversity to enrich learning and to produce results within the context of current school reform.⁴⁰

Methods of analysis. What do we expect to see in today's student-centered or learner-centered classroom?

- Students creating products that are meaningful to them
- Students confidently amplifying their voices, each in their own unique and genuine style
- Students thinking with complexity and applying knowledge and skills to new situations
- Students using tools to communicate in compelling ways
- Students reflecting on their learning and experiences through discovery

This change in perspective does not mean the teacher's role is diminished; actually, quite the opposite is true. Teachers have never been more essential to ensuring student outcomes.

Building the student-centered classroom

In every classroom, the most successful learning occurs when teachers are facilitators or activators of learning. Instead of giving formulaic sets of worksheets, tasks, or practice problems, teachers today are designing active, engaging learning experiences that build on student strengths and interests.

Results and analysis. During these learning experiences, students are empowered to think more complexly while creating and engaging with content through real-life problem solving and perseverance.

Below are four contributions teacher make to ensure that they create a structure in which student-centered classrooms thrive:

1. Creating a safe environment
2. Communicate learning goals
3. Provide a structure for feedback
4. Emphasize responsibility

Creating a safe environment

The foundation for any learning must be built in the context of a safe, nurturing classroom with positive, open communication. Learning is most meaningful and engaging when the classroom climate is one of welcoming errors and disconfirmation as a natural and positive part of developing and exercising new skills. As teachers, we

⁴⁰ Allen, D., and Tanner, K. 2005. Infusing Active Learning into the Large enrollment Biology Class. Seven Strategies, from Simple to Complex. *Journal of Life Science Education*, 4(4):262-268.

care deeply about our students, our work, and our goals. Our actions and efforts reflect the values of the school community, the classroom, and the education profession. By creating a mutually respectful classroom that embraces a diversity of thoughts and ideas, students can articulate their thinking judgment-free even if those thoughts may differ from others' thoughts and ideas.

Communicating learning goals

Because of this instructional and professional shift, it's important that teachers communicate the teacher-student relationship clearly. Establishing and sharing clear procedures with students early will set the structure for positive interactions and aspirations later.

From the start of the school year or when students first enroll in a class, clarify what the student expects from being in that class. This challenges conventional methods. Instead of the teacher telling the students what to expect, this approach begins the process of co-creating learning goals and proactively addresses any anxieties or misconceptions that students may have about the teacher, class, or content in general. The most successful teacher-student relationships are ones built on safety, trust, and respect. Those foundations are established only when students fully understand and share their teacher's vision for learning success.

Literature analysis. Another important aspect in establishing operating principles is for teachers to provide a structure and establish a frequency for communication and feedback with students and parents. In the past, teachers would communicate through grades, report cards, phone calls, or parent meetings at specific points throughout the year. Providing continuous feedback to students on a daily basis instead provides more specific, meaningful and productive feedback that leads to higher growth over time.

Fisher and Frey (2011) explain that feedback must be timely, understandable, and actionable. It's crucial that teachers give timely feedback throughout the problem-solving process, both in small groups and in individual conversations, and not just on a concluding assessment. This communication ensures students have time to react to and implement the feedback through revisions.

Conclusion. The specific or understandable nature of feedback ensures that students know exactly what parts of their reasoning need revision or what parts of their solution path contain inaccuracies. Actionable feedback ensures students can take an objective view of teacher or student feedback and immediately make changes. It's important language isn't vague or praising a student for the right answer. This is the appropriate time for clear, direct input, not praise or vague statements. Affirmation is important, but a separate part aspect of feedback.

Thought should be given to how feedback is delivered. Is it in conversation? If working in a google doc will the teacher provide comments in the document itself or in another creative platform? How often are academic or learning conferences held? Will feedback take precedence over grades? Will students be encouraged to reflect on feedback and how? These are structures, and expectations, that a teacher would explicitly communicate to students.

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